

THE DECLINE OF COMMUNAL TOMBS AND THE BYZANTINE-ISLAMIC
TRANSITION IN *PALAESTINA PRIMA/JUND FILASTĪN*

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ABSTRACT

Communal tombs were one of the more characteristic elements of material culture in ancient Palestine. Their quantitative analysis made it possible to reconstruct the dynamics of this burial from between the 4th and 10th centuries CE among populations of Judea, Samaria and the Coastal Plain. The results of this survey indicate that from the 5th century CE onwards, the number of new communal tomb foundations is gradually decreasing and the most recent date back to the early 7th century CE. Although some were still in use in the 8th century CE, they disappear completely in the following centuries.

Keywords: communal tombs, Palestine, Byzantine period, early Islamic period, family burials

RESUME

Les tombes communales étaient l'un des éléments les plus distinctifs de la culture matérielle en Palestine avant la conquête arabe. Leur analyse quantitative a permis de reconstituer la dynamique de leur développement entre le IV^e et le X^e siècle après J.-C. chez les populations de Judée, de Samarie et de la Plaine Côtière. Les résultats de cette étude indiquent qu'à partir du V^e siècle après J.-C., le nombre de nouvelles fondations de tombes communales diminue progressivement, les plus jeunes datant du début du VII^e siècle après J.-C. Bien que certaines d'entre elles soient encore utilisées au VIII^e siècle après J.-C., elles disparaissent complètement dans les siècles suivants.

Mots clés: tombes communales, Palestine, l'époque byzantine, débuts de l'époque islamique, sépultures familiales

1. Introduction

Since the publication of Hugh Kennedy's article on change in late antiquity cities of Syria-Palestine,¹ the issue of the cultural transformation in the Byzantine and early Islamic periods has been one of the most important research problems in the archaeology of this region. As until now, it has been considered in the context of change, of discontinuity and continuity in settlement, urban planning, economy and the form of everyday objects.² In this discussion, one of the main caesurae was the conquest of the

¹ Hugh KENNEDY, "From Polis to Madina: Urban Change in Late Antique and Early Islamic Syria", *Past and Present* 106 (1985), 3–27.

² E.g. Gideon AVNI, *The Byzantine-Islamic Transition in Palestine. An Archaeological Approach*,

Near East by Muslim Arabs in the second quarter of the 7th century CE. It is currently believed that this political watershed did not bring clear and immediate changes. Most of the settlements in Syria-Palestine were continuously inhabited by the local population. Although the form of the cities underwent transformation, this process had its roots in the Byzantine period. In the case of local craft production, in many cases, the continuity and evolutionary development of local forms in the early Islamic period is visible. In the area of religious life there were also no radical changes, as shown by the continuity of use of some of the Byzantine churches and synagogues. The small number of mosques built in the first decades after the Arab conquest points to a limited number of followers of Islam at that time. In the context of research into the Byzantine-Islamic transition in Syria-Palestine, however, the problem of burial habits has not been addressed. The aim of this article is to partially fill this gap by indicating significant changes in the sepulchral sphere in the period before and after the Arab conquest.

In antiquity, the most popular type of burial were individual pit-graves dug in the rock or soil, sometimes fitted with a stone walls and cover (cist-graves) (Fig. 1.A). Paradoxically, these are relatively rarely discovered by archaeologists, due to their modest form and limited visibility on the surface.³ Published examples of these are few in number, which makes them an unreliable basis for studying the transformation of burial customs. This research limitation does not apply to communal tomb. These were multi-person graves cut into rock or erected from stone (Fig. 1.B–E). As epigraphic sources indicate, they were used primarily for family burials,⁴ which was a popular practice in all of Greco-Roman Syria-Palestine.⁵ Rarely ever have burials of unrelated people been documented. These were mainly found in Byzantine monasteries.

The form and large size of communal tombs mean that they are discovered much more frequently by archaeologists than pit- and cist-graves. They therefore provide a

Oxford, Oxford University Press, 2014; James A. SAUER, Jodi MAGNESS, “Ceramics of the Islamic Period”, in: Eric M. MEYER (ed.), *The Oxford Encyclopedia of Archaeology in the Near East*, vol. 1, New York, Oxford, Oxford University Press, 1997, 475–479; Itarmar TAXEL, “Early Islamic Palestine: Toward a More Fine-tuned Recognition of Settlement Patterns and Land Uses in Town and Country”, *Journal of Islamic Archaeology* 5.2 (2018), 153–180, Alan WALMSLEY, *Early Islamic Syria: an Archaeological Assessment*, London, Duckworth, 2012.

³ On the considerable underestimation of the number of simpler forms of burial in ancient Palestine: Alexander FANTALKIN, “The Appearance of Rock-cut Bench Tombs in Iron Age Judah as a Reflection of State Formation”, in Alexander FANTALKIN, Assaf YASUR-LANDAU (ed.), *Bene Israel. Studies in the Archaeology of Israel and the Levant during the Bronze and Iron Ages in Honour of Israel Finkelstein* (Culture and History of the Ancient Near East, 31), Leiden, Boston, Brill, 20; Jodi MAGNESS, “Archaeological Invisible Burials”, in: Mayer GRUBER, Shmuel AHITUV, Gunnar LEHMANN, Zipora TALSHIR (ed.), *All the Wisdom of the East. Studies in Near Eastern Archaeology and History in Honor of Eliezer D. Oren* (Orbis Biblicus et Orientalis, 255), Fribourg, Academic Press Fribourg, 2012, 235–248.

⁴ Walter AMELING, Hannah COTTON, Werner ECK, Benjamin ISAAC, Alla KUSHNIR-STEIN, Haggai MISGAV, Jonathan PRICE, Ada YARDENI, *Corpus Inscriptionum Iudaeae/Palaestinae*, vol. 2: *Caesarea and the Middle Coast 1121-2160*, Berlin, Boston, de Gruyter, 2011, 419–420, 432, 486, ins. no 1476–1477, 1491, 1560; Walter AMELING, Hannah COTTON, Werner ECK, Benjamin ISAAC, Alla KUSHNIR-STEIN, Haggai MISGAV, Jonathan PRICE, Ada YARDENI, *Corpus Inscriptionum Iudaeae/Palaestinae* 3: *South Coast 2161-2648*, Berlin, Boston, de Gruyter, 2014, 37–38; Boaz ZISSU, Zubair ADAWI, “Two Rock-cut Burial Graves and Greek inscriptions from the Qidron Valley, Jerusalem”, *Atiqot* 78 (2014), 22–23; Oren SHMUELI, Eli YANNAI, Yifat PELEG, Yossi NAGAR, “Burial Caves from the Early Roman-Early Byzantine Periods at Ben Shemen” (in Hebrew with English summary), *Atiqot* 73 (2013), 136.

⁵ On family burials in the Roman period see: Michał GAWLIKOWSKI, *Monuments funéraires de Palmyre*. Warszawa, Państwowe Wydawnictwo Naukowe, 1970, 127, 146, 168–173; Annie SARTRE-FAURIAT, *Des tombeaux et des morts. Monuments funéraires, société et culture en Syrie du Sud du Ier s. Av. J.-C. Au VIIIe apr. J.-C.*, vol. 2: *synthèse* (Bibliothèque Archéologique et Historique, 158), Beyrouth, IFAPO, 2001, 180–182; Eyal REGEV, “Family Burial, Family Structure, and the Urbanization of Herodian Jerusalem”, *PEQ* 136.2 (2004), 109–131.

more credible basis for discussion of the changes in burial customs between the 4th and 10th centuries CE. The geographical scope of this study is limited to Judea, Samaria and the Palestinian Coastal Plain, where the province of *Palaestina Prima* was located in the Byzantine period and *Jund Filasṭīn* in the early Islamic period. This part of Syria-Palestine was inhabited by various ethno-religious groups, including Jews, Samaritans, and Christians. The area where the largest group of communal tombs in the Near East has been identified and archaeologically studied is now within the borders of Israel and the Palestinian Authority. This provides a credible sample to draw reliable conclusions about changes in some of burial customs.

2. Communal tombs in Judea, Samaria, and the Coastal Plain

The use of communal tombs in Palestine is one of the longer regional traditions. Their presence is already attested to in the Bronze Age and the Iron Age, when they were cut into rock.⁶ However, collective burials only began to spread on a wider scale in the Hellenistic period, reaching its peak in the Roman period. This is reflected in their varied internal and external form and the increase in their overall number. From the 3rd century BCE onwards, tombs with elongated niches (called *loculi* or *kokhim*) began to enjoy particular popularity (Fig. 1.B). In the following centuries, such tombs began to appear in large numbers, mainly in necropoleis near such cities as Jerusalem or Jericho,⁷ which were connected through Jewish political and religious elites. From the late 1st century BCE, small stone chests (*ossuaries*), into which bones were placed after the body had decomposed, became a permanent element of their furnishings.⁸ The form of the tombs themselves was a combination of local traditions and solutions from other parts of the Mediterranean. The source of inspiration for the appearance of *loculi/kokhim* could be Phoenician tombs,⁹ whereby the influence of Egypt, whose rulers in the 3rd and first half of the 2nd century BCE also controlled Palestine, is more likely. This interpretation is supported by the presence of the best analogies in the Hellenistic cemeteries of Alexandria.¹⁰

Inscriptions from the end of the 1st century BCE and the 1st century CE appearing in such tombs indicate unequivocally that the related burials were of a family nature.¹¹ Moreover, they also show that in many cases these families were linked to the elite of the Jewish community, including the High Priests.¹² It took many days of work to build such tombs and, consequently, a considerable financial commitment. This confirms that they were linked to more affluent groups in society. In Palestine during the Roman period, equally expensive mausoleums, i.e., free-standing tombs built from stone blocks, also became widespread.¹³

⁶ Elizabeth BLOCH-SMITH, *Judahite Burial Practices and Beliefs about the Dead* (JSOT.S, 123), Sheffield, JSOT Press, 1992, 41–52; Rivka GONEN, *Burial Patterns and Cultural Diversity in Late Bronze Age Canaan* (ASOR Dissertation Series, 7), Winona Lake, Indiana, Eisenbrauns, 1992, 9–15.

⁷ Amos KLONER, Boaz ZISSU, *The Necropolis of Jerusalem in the Second Temple Period* (Interdisciplinary Studies in Ancient Culture and Religion, 8), Leuven-Dudley, Peeters, 2007; Rachel HACHLILI, Ann E. KILLEBREW, *Jericho. The Jewish Cemetery of the Second Temple Period* (IAA Reports, 7), Jerusalem, Israel Antiquities Authority, 1999.

⁸ Rachel HACHLILI, *Jewish Funerary Customs, Practices and Rites in the Second Temple Period* (JSJ.S, 94), Leiden-Boston, Brill, 2005, 94–115.

⁹ Oren TAL, “On the Origin and Concept of the Loculi Tombs of Hellenistic Palestine”, *Ancient West & East* 2.2 (2003), 288–307.

¹⁰ Marjorie S. VENIT, *Monumental Tombs of Ancient Alexandria. The Theater of the Dead*, Cambridge, Cambridge University Press, 2002, 9–34.

¹¹ E. REGEV, “Family Burial”, 109–131.

¹² R. HACHLILI, *Jewish Funerary Customs*, 262, 295, 299.

¹³ E.g. Etan AYALON, “A Roman-Byzantine Mausoleum at Kh. Sabiya, Kefar Sava” (in Hebrew with

A similar development in sepulchral architecture during the Roman period is also documented in other parts of Syria-Palestine. The most spectacular tombs, in terms of their number and quality of finishing, were usually located in cemeteries near settlements of significant political importance. The best examples of this are Palmyra in Syria and Petra in Arabia.¹⁴ The spread of communal tombs is itself linked to the growing importance of the need for self-presentation and honouring the memory of the deceased members of the immediate family, which in some cases is clearly indicated by inscriptions.¹⁵

In Judea, the dynamic development of family tombs was partly halted by the defeat of the First Jewish Revolt in 70 CE. The consequences of this event are clearly visible in the great necropoleis of Jerusalem, where most of the tombs erected earlier were abandoned. This is directly linked to the massacre and resettlement of a large part of the Jewish population by the Romans. In a few cases, such tombs were reused in the 2nd–4th centuries CE by pagan soldiers and settlers arriving from other parts of the Roman Empire. This is indicated by the appearance of cremation burials at that time, which were not used by the Semitic population in the Near East during the Roman period.¹⁶

Some of the family tombs from Judea were still in use after 70 CE.¹⁷ Despite everything, this indicates that the use of communal tombs in this part of Palestine continued. This was not only among Samaritans and pagans, but also Jews. In the case of the latter, this is documented, among other places, in southern Judea, where ossuaries have been found in tombs from the 2nd to 4th centuries CE.¹⁸

In the Byzantine period, there is also a very clear continuation of the use of tombs cut into rock for multi-person burials. Over time, the troughs, i.e., rectangular niches for corpses parallel to the tomb walls (Fig. 1.C), become commonplace in such structures.¹⁹ At this time, the construction of mausoleums with decorated facades erected from stone blocks, is much less frequently documented. Although in the southern part of the

English summary), *Atiqot* 25 (1994), 27*–39*, 189–190; Avraham EITAN, “Excavations at the Foot of Tel Rosh Ha’ayin” (in Hebrew with English summary), *Atiqot* 5 (1969), 49–67, 6*–7*; Mordechai HAIMAN, “Binyamina”, *Hadashot Arkheologiyot* 121 (2009), s.p.; Rober W. HAMILTON, “The Domed Tomb at Sebastya”, *The Quarterly of the Department of Antiquities in Palestine* 8 (1939), 64–71; Izchak MAGEN, *Flavia Neapolis. Shechem in the Roman Period*, vol. 1 (Judea and Samaria Publications, 11), Jerusalem, Israel Antiquities Authority, 2009, 289–297; Sa’ar NUDEL, “Binyamina, Giv’at Ha-Po’alim” (in Hebrew with English summary), *Hadashot Arkheologiyot* 109 (1999), 54–57, 40*; Yuval PELEG, Uzi GREENFELD, “A Roman Mausoleum in Kh. Kafr Qara” (in Hebrew with English summary), *Judea and Samaria Research Studies* 23 (2014), XV–XIV, 143–157.

¹⁴ M. GAWLIKOWSKI, *Monuments funéraires de Palmyre*; Lucy WADESON, “Nabataean Façade Tombs: a New Chronology”, *Studies in the History and Archaeology* 11 (2013), 507–528, with further references.

¹⁵ Lidewijde DE JONG, *The Archaeology of Death in Roman Syria. Burial, Commemoration, and Empire*, Cambridge, Cambridge University Press, 2017, 172–173, 209; R. HACHILLI, *Jewish Funerary Customs*, 301.

¹⁶ Shlomit WEKSLER-BDOLAH, *Aelia Capitolina – Jerusalem in the Roman Period. In Light of Archaeological Research* (Mnemosyne Supplements, 432), Leiden, Boston, Brill, 2020, 151–168, 203–204, with further references.

¹⁷ E.g. Gideon AVNI, Uzi DAHARI, Amos KLONER, *The Necropolis of Bet Guvrin-Eleutheropolis* (IAA Reports, 36), Jerusalem, Israel Antiquity Authority, 2008, 119; Yuval BARUCH, “A Burial Cave of the Roman Period on the Outskirts of el-Kirmil” (in Hebrew with English summary), *Atiqot* 32 (1997), 91–94, 42*; Yuval BARUCH, Amir GANOR, “Jerusalem, Khirbat ‘Addasa”, *Hadashot Arkheologiyot* 120 (2008), s.p.

¹⁸ Peter FABIAN, Haim GOLDFUS, “The Cemetery of Horbat Rimmon in the Southern Judean Shephelah”, *Atiqot* 46 (2004), 96*; Ram GOPHNA, Varda SUSSMAN, “A Jewish Burial Cave of the Roman period at the Foot of Tel Halif” (In Hebrew with English summary), *Atiqot* 7 (1974), 12*.

¹⁹ Hans-Peter KUHNEN, *Studien zur Chronologie und Siedlungsarchäologie des Karmel (Israel) zwischen Hellenismus und Spätantike* (Beihefte zum Tübinger Atlas des Vorderen Orients, 19), Wiesbaden, Dr. Ludwig Reichert Verlag, 1989, 172–174.

Palestinian Coast since the 3rd–4th century CE hypogea with barrel vaults and troughs were most often built (Fig. 1.D), which is characteristic for the region.²⁰

The appearance of Christianity at the beginning of the 1st millennium CE and the clear increase in the number of followers of this religion in the 4th and subsequent centuries was not linked to widespread and clear changes in burial customs.²¹ In most cases, the communal tombs of the Byzantine period are a continuation of older traditions. This is evidenced by the fact that tombs cut in stone from previous eras were reused.²² In some cases, they were enriched with decorations with Christian motifs, among which crosses were most popular.

At the necropolis in Bet Guvrin, in several tombs, the co-occurrence of oil lamps with Jewish and Christian religious symbols was noted. This may indicate that there were no contraindications to burying Christians in graves previously used by Jews.²³ In the Byzantine period, completely new communal tombs of a family nature were also erected.²⁴ This custom was continued not only by Christians, but also by Samaritans, as shown by discoveries, for example, on the Central Coastal Plain.²⁵ Nor was the custom of family burials forgotten among the Jewish population, as evidenced by the inscriptions discovered on the Abu Kabir necropolis in Jaffa, dating from the 4th to the 6th century CE.²⁶

In the Byzantine period, there were also unusually large communal tombs. The best example of this is the so-called Tomb of the Prophets cut into the eastern necropolis of Jerusalem. Based on the inscriptions found inside, it was established that it was intended for the burial of Christian pilgrims who had been visiting the Holy Land in large

²⁰ Yaakov HUSTER, Ofer SION, “Late Roman and Byzantine Period Vaulted Tombs in the Southern Coastal Plain” (in Hebrew with English summary), *Jerusalem and Eretz-Israel: A Journal for Land of Israel Studies and Archaeology* 3 (2006), 7, 49–67.

²¹ On the christianization of Palestine see: Doron BAR, “The Christianization of Rural Palestine during Late Antiquity”, *Journal of Ecclesiastical History* 54.3 (2003), 420; Joseph PATRICH, Tamar BACKNER, Sharon BURGER, Svetlana TARKHANOVA, “Churches of the Holy Land. A New Digital Corpus. Introduction and Some Preliminary Results”, in: Alessandro CONIGLIO, Amedeo RICCO (ed.), *Holy Land Archaeology on Either Side. Archaeological Essays in Honour of Eugenio Alliata, ofm* (Studium Biblicum Franciscanum, Collectio Maior, 57), Milano, Edizioni Terra Santa, 2020, 28.

²² E.g. Shahar BATZ, “Continuity and Change in Burial Rites in the Northern Hebron Hills, from Iron Age II until the Byzantine Period” (in Hebrew with English summary), *Judea and Samaria Research Studies* 16 (2007), XI–XII, 43–58.

²³ Jodi MAGNESS, “The Oil Lamps from the South Cemetery”, in: Gideon AVNI, Uzi DAHARI, Amos KLONER (ed.), *The Necropolis of Bet Guvrin-Eleutheropolis* (IAA Reports, 36), Jerusalem, Israel Antiquity Authority, 2008, 133.

²⁴ E.g. Gideon AVNI, Uzi DAHARI, “Christian Burial Caves from the Byzantine Period at Luzit”, in: Giovanni C. BOTTINI, Leah DI SEGNI, Eugenio ALLIATA, (ed.), *Christian Archaeology in the Holy Land New Discoveries* (Studium Biblicum Franciscanum, Collectio Maior, 36), Jerusalem, Franciscan Printing Press, 1990, 301–314; Dan BARAG, “A Tomb Cave of the Byzantine Period Near Netiv Ha-Lamed He” (in Hebrew with English summary), *’Atiqot* 7 (1974), 13*, 81–87, Eitan KLEIN, “Khirbat Deir Sallam East”, *Hadashot Arkheologiyot* 127 (2015), s.p., Jon SELIGMAN, Joe ZIAS, Harley STARK, “Late Hellenistic and Byzantine Burial Caves, at Giv’at Sharet, Bet Shemesh”, *’Atiqot* 29 (1996), 43–62; Gideon SOLIMANY, “A Burial Cave from the Byzantine and Early Islamic Periods in Horbat Gores, the Gonen Quarter, Jerusalem” (in Hebrew with English summary), *’Atiqot* 54 (2006), 87*–94*, 161–163; Gideon SOLIMANY, “A Burial Cave from the Byzantine–Early Islamic Periods at ‘En Lavan, Nahal Refa‘im” (in Hebrew with English summary), *’Atiqot* 98 (2020), 1*–8*, 171–172.

²⁵ Oren TAL, Itamar TAXEL, *Samaritan Cemeteries and Tombs in the Central Coastal Plain.*

Archaeology and History of the Samaritan Settlement outside Samaria (ca. 300–700 CE) (Ägypten und Altes Testament, 82), Münster, Ugarit-Verlag, 2015, 195–202.

²⁶ Avner ECKER, “The Necropolis of the Hill of Abu Kabir”, in: Orit TSUF, (ed.), *Ancient Jaffa from the Persian to the Byzantine Period. Kaplan Excavations (1955–1981)* (Ägypten und Altes Testament, 89), Münster, Zaphon, 2018, 636–637.

numbers since the 4th century CE.²⁷ Another example of this kind of tomb is connected with the northern outskirts of Jerusalem. In this area, an inscription was discovered that mentions a tomb belonging to the *xenodocheion* that cared for pilgrims.²⁸ Both examples suggest the existence of communal tombs at that time used to bury Christians who were not related.

With the development of Palestinian monasticism, another group of communal tombs appeared. These were usually crypts located within the monasteries where members of a given monastic community were buried.²⁹ Such collective burials are a testimony to the formation of new social relations within the monastic communities and are a particular example of the abandonment of family burials. This was a natural result of the monks' way of living and their partial separation from their relatives. It should also be remembered that many people living in Palestinian monasteries came from other parts of the Mediterranean.³⁰

In the Roman period, as mentioned earlier, communal tombs were associated with the burials of well-off families. However, examples related to pilgrims and monasteries show that in the Byzantine period, the proximity of family members was not the only reason for collective burials. This can be linked to the Christian tendency to create a posthumous relationship with God rather than with one's own kinship.³¹

In the 7th century CE, including after the Arab conquest of the Province of *Palaestina Prima*, the custom of using communal tombs did not cease. This applied both to those of a family nature and those associated with monastic communities.³² Testimony to this is, among other things, the findings of oil lamps dating back to the 7th and 8th centuries CE in such tombs. Such cases have been recorded both in urban and rural cemeteries.

3. Quantification of communal tombs in Byzantine *Palaestina Prima* and early Islamic *Jund Filasṭīn*

²⁷ Gideon AVNI, Boaz ZISSU, "The "Tombs of the Prophets" on the Mount of Olives. A Re-examination", in: Ann E. KILLEBREW, Gabriele FABBECK, G. (ed.), *Viewing Ancient Jewish Art and Archaeology. VeHinnei Rachel – Essays in Honor of Rachel Hachlili* (JSJ.S, 172), Leiden, Boston, Brill, 2016, 16–32.

²⁸ Hannah COTTON, Leah DI SEGNI, Werner ECK, Benjamin ISAAC, Alla KUSHNIR-STEIN, Haggai MISGAV, Jonathan PRICE, Ada YARDENI, *Corpus Inscriptionum Iudaeae/Palaestinae, vol. 1: Jerusalem, part 2: 705–1120*, New York, Boston, De Gruyter, 2012, 393–394, ins. no 1008.

²⁹ E.g. Yizhar HIRSCHFELD, *The Judean Desert Monasteries in the Byzantine Period*, New Haven, London, Yale University Press, 1992, 130–143; Amit RE'EM, "Jerusalem, the Third Wall", *Hadashot Arkheologiyot* 121 (2009), s.p.; Jon SELIGMAN, "A Georgian Monastery from the Byzantine Period at Khirbat Umm Leisun, Jerusalem", *'Atiqot* 83 (2015), 145–179.

³⁰ Y. HIRSCHFELD, *The Judean Desert Monasteries*, 10–15.

³¹ Yvette DUVAL, Y. 1988. *Auprès des saints corps et âme. L'inhumation « ad sanctos » dans la chrétienté d'Orient et d'Occident du III^e au VII^e siècle* (ÉAug), Paris, Institut d'Études Augustiniennes, 1988; Éric REBILLARD, *Religion et sépulture. L'Églises, les vivants et les morts dans l'Antiquité tardive* (Civilisations et Sociétés, 115), Paris, Éditions de l'École des Hautes Études en Sciences Sociales, 2003, 42–45.

³² Examples of family graves: G. AVNI, U. DAHARI, "Christian Burial Caves", 301–314; Zvi GREENHUT, Boaz ZISSU, "Ramat Razi'el", *Hadashot Arkheologiyot* 116 (2004), s.p.; I. MAGEN, *Flavia Neapolis*, 93–305; Ofer SION, Abd el Rahim HAMRAN, A. 1995. "Khirbet Kheibar", *Excavations and Surveys in Israel* 14 (1995), 74, G. SOLIMANY, "A Burial Cave", 1*–8*, 171–172. Examples of monastic graves: E.g. Uzi DAHARI, Yehiel ZELINGER, "The Excavation at Horvat Ḥani – Final Report and a Survey on Nuns and Nunneries in Israel", in: Giovanni C.BOTTINI, Daniel CHRUPCALA, Joseph PATRICH (ed.), *Knowledge and Wisdom: Archaeological and Historical Essays in Honour of Leah di Segni* (Studium Biblicum Franciscanum, Collectio Maior, 54), Milano, Edizioni Terra Santa, 2014, 179–203; Izchak MAGEN, "A Roman Fortress and a Byzantine monastery at Khirbet el-Kiliya", in: Noga CARMIN (ed.), *Christians and Christianity, vol. 3. Churches and Monasteries in Samaria and Northern Judea* (Judea and Samaria Publications, 15), Jerusalem, Israel Antiquities Authority, 2012, 261–296.

The transformations described above and the continuity of collective burial practices in Judea, Samaria and the Palestinian Coast present an image of the qualitative state of the matter. Based on the quantification of the communal tombs, it is possible to recreate the dynamics of the development of this tradition and its connection to contemporary historical events and those related to settlement and demographics. For this purpose, the *Chamber Tombs Data Base* was used, which is a catalogue of dated constructions of this type at Syro-Palestinian sites from first millennium BCE and first millennium CE.³³ It includes 3,430 different types of tombs, whereby only part of this data base has been used to analyse the situation in *Palaestina Prima/Jund Filasṭīn*. The selection criteria were the borders of the studied region and the basis for dating of the individual tombs. At least 667 communal tombs from the period between the 4th and 10th century CE were identified in this area (Fig. 2). In many cases, their dating was based on grave form typologies. Such a method can be applied quite well in the case of attempts to determine an approximate date for the construction of tombs subsequently plundered by robbers. Nevertheless, it is almost impossible to determine the exact time they were in use.

Therefore, selected tombs were used for the analysis, for which the time of their use can be determined on the basis of the coins, glass or ceramic vessels found in them. Particularly important in this respect were the various forms of oil lamps with reliably precise production chronology that appear frequently in communal tombs.³⁴ Currently, 257 tombs meet these criteria, connected with 94 sites in the area of *Palaestina Prima/Jund Filasṭīn* (Table 1) (Fig. 2), which is over 1/3 of all those registered in this region in the *Chamber Tombs Data Base*. This number is large enough to allow general conclusions to be drawn regarding trends in the chronology of their use.

In the quantitative analysis covering the period from the 4th century CE to the 10th century CE, three data sets broken down by individual centuries were considered. These were: 1. total number of communal tombs in use; 2. number of new foundations; 3. number of abandoned tombs. Each of these data sets allows reconstruction of the history of group burials from a different perspective. It should be noted that the first and third data sets include tombs built before the 4th century CE, with the phases of use occurring in the Byzantine period.

Between the 4th and 7th centuries CE, the number of used tombs in the selected data set remains at a relatively high level, ranging from 107 to 192 (Fig. 3). The largest number of used tombs (n 192) and those newly created (n 63) falls in the 4th century CE (Fig. 4). However, as many as 129 of these had been constructed in the Roman period, or even earlier. In subsequent centuries a progressive decline in the number of tombs used is visible (Fig. 3). A similar downward trend was also observed in the case of new foundations in the 5th and 6th centuries CE (Fig. 4). Moreover, in the 7th century CE and the following centuries, such construction activity practically comes to a complete halt. At the same time, it should be noted that between the 4th and 10th centuries CE no drastic increase in the number of abandoned tombs in various parts of this region is noted (Fig. 5). This process was evenly distributed over several centuries.

The quantitative analysis above shows that starting in the 5th century CE in *Palaestina Prima* there is a clear trend of a decreasing number of newly founded tombs and total

³³ Mariusz GWIAZDA, *Chamber Tombs Data Base* [online], Available at www.chambertombs.uw.edu.pl [Accessed 22 February 2021]; Mariusz GWIAZDA, "Dataset of Syro-Palestinian Chamber Tombs from the First Millennium BCE and CE", *Journal of Open Archaeology Data* 8.1 (2020), 1–8.

³⁴ E.g. Jodi MAGNESS, "The Oil Lamps", 179–186; Varda SUSSMAN, *Late Roman to Late Byzantine/Early Islamic Period Lamps in the Holy Land. The Collection of the Israel Antiquities Authority* (Archaeopress Archaeology), Oxford, Archaeopress, 2017.

number of tombs in use. These phenomena are also accompanied by a slow process of abandoning tombs constructed in previous centuries. A result of this was the near complete abandonment of the tradition of communal burials in the early Islamic period. Their continued use at the end of the first millennium CE is attested to in a few monasteries (E.g. monasteries of St. Euthymius and St. George of Choziba).

4. Context of the disappearance of communal tombs

Quantitative analysis indicates the existence of two processes leading to a qualitative change in the sepulchral landscape of the provinces of *Palaestina Prima* and *Jund Filastīn*. First, there is a gradual decrease in the number of newly founded communal tombs in the Byzantine period. Second, the final period when they were in use lies in the 7th–8th centuries CE. Both phenomena were spread out over time and require separate attempts at explanation.

The collapse of the tradition of communal burials primarily concerns family tomb foundations by Christians, Jews and Samaritans alike. This same phenomenon is a manifestation of a broader transformation that did not have a solely religious basis and did not belong to a single religious group. Unlike simpler forms of individual burials, the foundation of a family tomb was conditioned on access to appropriate financial resources and on the very need to bury the deceased together with their nearest of kin. Thus, it can be assumed that a problem with one or both of these factors in the Byzantine period led to the disappearance of the construction of family tombs.

However, written sources, let alone archaeological sources, do not provide a clear explanation as to why part of the population of this region increasingly rarely decided to establish common graves for their spouses and children. With all certainty, no aversion to this type of burial appeared between the 5th and 8th centuries CE. Such a change in attitude would have resulted in an earlier and more sudden abandonment of communal tombs. However, after they were built, in many cases they were still used in the early Islamic period. This reflects an attachment to this burial tradition rather than a sudden rejection of it.

In the Byzantine period, a spread of the custom of communal burials within monastic communities is visible. The increase in these corresponds to the clear growth in the number of monasteries in the Holy Land in the 5th and 6th centuries CE. However, the formation of this new practice, in which corpses were placed in collective tombs without taking into account blood ties, could not have had a significant impact on the gradual reduction in the number of family tombs. This is because the change only affected one of the three religious groups in the region, namely Christians. Moreover, the great popularity of the monastic movement in Palestine in the Byzantine period did not lead to the collapse of the traditional form of social organisation that was the family.

Another phenomenon characteristic of the Byzantine period was the appearance of cist-graves with the bodies of men, women and children in churches. According to Haim Goldfus, such a privilege was granted to the clergy and those who financed the construction of such buildings.³⁵ Moreover, in Palestine between the 5th and the beginning of the 7th century CE, based on dated foundation inscriptions, increased construction activity can be observed. This was focused on religious buildings – mainly churches.³⁶

³⁵ Haim GOLDFUS, “Burials in Ordinary Churches and Monastic Complexes of Byzantine Palestine: a Synthesis”, in: Reinhardt HARREITHER, Philippe PERGOLA, Renate PILLINGER, Andreas PÜLZ (ed.), *Akten des XIV. Internationalen Kongresses für Christliche Archäologie. Wien 19.-26.9.1999. Frühes Christentum zwischen Rom und Konstantinopel*, vol. 1 (Studi di Antichità Cristiana, 62), Wien, Vatican, Pontificio Istituto di Archeologia Cristiana, 2006, 414–415.

³⁶ Leah DI SEGNI, “Epigraphic Documentation on Building in the Provinces of Palaestina and Arabia, 4th–

This may suggest that for wealthy Christians, sponsorship of church institutions grew in importance. Thus, the reduction in the number of new family tombs cannot be linked to financial crisis. More likely is a change in mentality of part of the Palestinian population, including the way in which the financial surpluses at their disposal were invested.³⁷

The final period of the abandonment of communal tombs in the 7th to 8th century CE should not come as a surprise. A similar phenomenon can be observed in the case of churches in the Holy Land. Of the 294 buildings of this type with confirmed use in the 7th century CE, 140 were abandoned in that same century. In the case of some, it was possible to associate their abandonment with the conquest of Palestine by the Persians and Arabs in the first half of the 7th century CE.³⁸ At the same time, the remaining half of the churches, in the same or modified form, were used later. Only in a few cases is the construction of new churches in the 7th and 8th centuries CE also certified.³⁹ This indicates the continued presence of Christians in the region, but with a reduced number of religious buildings used by them in the early Islamic period. In the case of monasteries in the 7th and 8th centuries CE, it also came to the abandonment of some.⁴⁰ However, the important role of monks in the life of the Christian community of Palestine at that time was not shaken.⁴¹ In the southern part of *Palaestina Prima/Jund Filastīn*, where the Jewish presence was concentrated, a similar phenomenon can be observed in the case of synagogues. Those in En-Gedi, Rimmon, Gaza-Maiumas, Ma'on-Nirim and probably in Ma'on and 'Anim were abandoned in the 7th century CE, whereby in places such as Susiya, Eshtemoa, Na'aran and Jericho, they operated until at least the 8th century CE.⁴²

Undoubtedly, the first half of the 7th century CE was a difficult period for the people of Palestine. After the conquest of the Levant by the Persians in 614 CE, migration by the local population is attested. In the first place, the destination of their flight was Egypt and in the next stage also the western provinces of Byzantium. Certainly, emigration was chosen by those few who could afford to pay the cost of long journeys.⁴³ This crisis was

7th c.”, in: John H. HUMPHREY (ed.), *The Roman and Byzantine Near East: Some Recent Archaeological Research*, vol. 2 (JRA.S, 31), Portsmouth, Rhode Island, Journal of Roman Archaeology, 1999, 149–178; Leah DI SEGNI, “Late Antique Inscriptions in the Provinces of *Palaestina* and *Arabia*: Realities and Change”, in: Katharina BOLLE, Carlos MACHADO, Christian WITSCHERL (ed.), *The Epigraphic Cultures of Late Antiquity* (Heidelberger Althistorische Beiträge, 60), Stuttgart, Franz Steiner Verlag, 2017, 287–320, 609–615.

³⁷ See Antigone SAMELLAS, *Death in the Eastern Mediterranean (50–600 A.D.). The Christianization of the East: An Interpretation* (Studies and Texts in Antiquity and Christianity, 12), Tübingen, Mohr Siebeck, 2002, 135.

³⁸ Sharon BURGER, “Architectural Changes in the Churches of the Holy Land in the Transition from the Byzantine to Islamic rule”, in: Alessandro CONIGLIO, Amedeo RICCO (ed.), *Holy Land Archaeology on Either Side. Archaeological Essays in Honour of Eugenio Alliata, ofm* (Studium Biblicum Franciscanum, Collectio Maior, 57), Milano, Edizioni Terra Santa, 2020, 134–136; see also Robert SCHICK, *The Christian Communities of Palestine from Byzantine to Islamic Rule: A Historical and Archaeological Study* (Studies in Late Antiquity and Early Islam, 2), Princeton, Darwin Press, 1995, 220.

³⁹ Sh. BURGER, “Architectural Changes”, 140–141.

⁴⁰ Joseph PATRICH, “The Impact of the Muslim Conquest on Monasticism in the Desert of Jerusalem”, in: Antoine BORRUT, Muriel DEBIE, Arietta PAPAConstantinou, Dominic PIERI, Jean-Pierre SODINI (ed.), *Le Proche-Orient de Justinien aux Abbassides. Peuplement et dynamiques spatiales* (Bibliothèque de l'Antiquité Tardive, 19), Turnhout, Brepols, 2011, 208–217.

⁴¹ Brouria BITTON-ASHKELONY, Aryeh KOFKY, “Monasticism in the Holy Land”, in: Ora LIMOR, Guy G. STROUMSA (ed.), *Christians and Christianity in the Holy Land. From the Origins to the Latin Kingdoms* (Cultural Encounters in Late Antiquity and the Middle Ages, 5), Turnhout, Brepols, 2006, 287–291.

⁴² Steven H. WERLIN, *Ancient Synagogues of Southern Palestine, 300–800 CE. Living on the Edge* (The Brill Reference Library of Judaism, 47), Leiden, Boston, Brill, 2015, 300–301.

⁴³ Phil BOOTH, *Crisis of Empire. Doctrine and Dissent at the End of Late Antiquity* (Transformation of the Classical Heritage, 52), Berkeley, Los Angeles, London, University of California Press, 2014, 98;

also reflected in the increased number of coin hoards associated with the Persian conquest and occupation of Palestine.⁴⁴ Such discoveries clearly testify to discontinuity, which is expressed by the inability to recover and use these coin deposits at a later date. This could have been linked to both irreversible emigration as well as the death of their owners. The latter possibility is well documented in Mamilla Neighbourhood in Jerusalem. The most recent example of a communal tomb in the analysed data set is related to this city. It was a chapel in directly connected to a burial cave filled with piles of human bones. The establishment of this burial complex is linked to the massacre of the Christian population during the Persian invasion. Such a chronological attribution is supported by the coins, oil lamps and inscriptions discovered here.⁴⁵ In other parts of Jerusalem, more mass graves and traces of destruction associated with these events have also been found.⁴⁶

The assertion that in *Jund Filasṭīn* there was either uninterrupted continuity or a collapse of settlement in the 7th – 8th century CE would be far from the truth. In many different parts of this region, traces of each of these scenarios have been identified. An example of a settlement crisis linked to the disappearance of family tombs is the southern part of the Palestinian Coast near to Gaza and Ashkelon. In this region, starting in the 3rd–4th century CE, barrel vaulted hypogea were built in urban and rural cemeteries.⁴⁷ This region was known for the production of wine exported on a massive scale to other parts of the Mediterranean in the so-called Late Roman Amphorae 4.⁴⁸ This regional production collapsed in the 7th century CE,⁴⁹ which must have had a negative impact on the prosperity of wealthy landowners in the region. This coincides with the abandonment of tombs of this type. This is well illustrated by the example of what is known as the ‘Third Mile Estate’ in vicinity of Ashqelon, abandoned in the 7th century CE, where winepresses, kilns for the production of LRA 4 and three hypogea with barrel vaults were all found.⁵⁰

The traces of use of family tombs constructed in earlier centuries also disappear in other parts of the Palestinian Coast in the 7th century CE (Fig. 6). The reason for this was certainly partial settlement discontinuity and contraction in this area associated with political instability. With the retreat of Byzantine troops under Arab pressure, part of the local population fled from the coast as well, as confirmed by written and archaeological sources.⁵¹ The resulting gaps in settlement were filled by the Arab administration through

Panagiotis THEODOROPOULOS, “The Migration of Syrian and Palestinian Population in the 7th century: Movement of Individuals and Groups in the Mediterranean”, in: Johannes Preiser-KAPPELLER, Lucian REINFANDT, Yannis STOURAITIS (ed.), *Migration Histories of the Medieval Afroeurasian Transition Zone. Aspects of Mobility between Africa, Asia and Europe, 300-1500 C.E.* (Studies in Global Migration History, 13), Leiden, Brill, 2020, 262–284.

⁴⁴ Gabriela BIJOVSKY, *Gold Coin and Small Change: Monetary Circulation in Fifth-Seventh Century Byzantine Palestine* (Polymnia Numismatica Antica e Medievale, Studi, 2), Trieste, Edizioni Università di Trieste, 2012, 422–425, 444.

⁴⁵ Ronny REICH, “The Ancient Burial Ground in the Mamilla Neighborhood, Jerusalem”, in: Hillel GEVA, (ed.), *Ancient Jerusalem Revealed*, Jerusalem, Israel Exploration Society, 1994, 117–118.

⁴⁶ Gideon AVNI, “The Persian Conquest of Jerusalem (614 C.E). An Archaeological Assessment”, *BASOR* 357 (2010), 35–48; Elena KOGAN-ZEHAVID, “A Burial Cave of the Byzantine Period in the Naḥalat Aḥim” (in Hebrew with English summary), *Atiqot* 54 (2006), 61*–86*, 160–161.

⁴⁷ Y. HUSTER, O. SION, “Late Roman and Byzantine Period Vaulted Tombs”, 49–67.

⁴⁸ Sean A. KINGSLEY, *A Sixth-Century AD Shipwreck off the Carmel Coast, Israel. Dor D and Holy Land Wine Trade* (BAR International Series, 1065), Oxford, Archaeopress, 2002, 81.

⁴⁹ Chris WICKHAM, *Framing the Early Middle Ages. Europe and the Mediterranean, 400–800*, Oxford, Oxford University Press, 2005, 716–774.

⁵⁰ Yigal ISRAEL, Tali ERICKSON-GINI, “Remains from the Hellenistic through the Byzantine Periods at the ‘Third Mile Estate’”, Ashqelon, *Atiqot* 74 (2013), 201–203.

⁵¹ Milka LEVY-RUBIN, “Changes in the Settlement Pattern of Palestine Following the Arab conquest”, in: Kenneth G. HOLM, Hayim LAPIN (ed.), *Shaping the Middle East. Jews, Christians, and Muslims in an*

the resettlement of people, including Muslims, from other parts of the newly formed empire.

The results of surveys and archaeological excavations in the Judean Desert also show clear signs of discontinuity in case of many sites.⁵² This was the case, among others, for a large part of the monasteries mentioned earlier. Undoubtedly, this was the reason for the simultaneous abandonment of the associated crypts established in the Byzantine period. On the other hand, in the same micro-region, there are also clear traces of development in Jericho and its vicinity. The best example of this is the construction by the Umayyads in the first half of the 8th century CE of a palace and agricultural complex at Khirbet el-Mafjar.⁵³ However, the appearance of this new settlement was not connected with the establishment of new communal tombs. Likewise, at the capital of *Jund Filasṭīn* in Ramla, founded in 715 CE, archaeologists to date have only come across individual pit-graves.⁵⁴ This is despite there being family tombs from earlier eras in the vicinity of the town.⁵⁵

This was linked to the different customs of the Arab-Muslim population slowly arriving in Palestine. Both archaeological findings and Arabic written sources indicate that this ethno-religious group had the custom of burying the dead in single-person pits dug in the ground. It was also important to orient the body on an east-west axis, with its head facing Mecca.⁵⁶ The construction of more imposing monuments over such graves was a rare practice criticised by orthodox Muslims.⁵⁷

A poorly understood problem is the Islamisation of the *Jund Filasṭīn* population after the Arab conquest. Only very limited sources shed light on this phenomenon. The small number of mosques built between the second half of the 7th and 8th centuries CE is particularly notable. Their emergence was linked to an influx of Arabs, not to the conversion of the local populace to Islam. Mass conversion applied mainly to the Samaritan population. Thanks to written sources we know that this took place mainly in the 9th and 10th centuries CE and was motivated by economic factors.⁵⁸ Thus, there is no indication that Islamisation could have had a significant and direct impact on changing the burial habits of local people in earlier centuries.

Age of Transition 400–800 C.E., Bethesda, Maryland, University Press of Maryland, 2011, 155–172; Itarmar TAXEL, “The Byzantine-Early Islamic Transition on the Palestinian Coastal Plain: a Re-evaluation of the Archaeological Evidence”, *Semitica et Classica* 6 (2013), 73–106; Itarmar TAXEL, “Rural Settlement Processes in Central Palestine, ca. 640–800 C.E.: The Ramla-Yavneh Region as a Case Study”, *BASOR* 369 (2013), 191–192; P. THEODOROPOULOS, “The Migration of Syrian”, 265–268.

⁵² Itarmar TAXEL, “The Byzantine-Early Islamic Transition in the Dead Sea region”, in: Martin PEILSTÖCKER, Sabine WOLFRAM, (ed.), *Life at the Dead Sea. Proceedings of the International Conference held at the State Museum of Archaeology Chemnitz (smac), February 21–24, 2018*, Chemnitz (Ägypten und Altes Testament, 96), Münster, Zaphon, 2019, 297–300, 311, with further references.

⁵³ See Donald WHITCOMB, Michael JENNINGS, Andrew CREEKMORE, Ignacio ARCE, “Khirbet al-Mafjar. New Excavations and Hypotheses for an Umayyad Monument”, *Near Eastern Archaeology* 79.2 (2016), 78–87, with further references.

⁵⁴ Alexander ONN, “Ramla”, *Hadashot Arkheologiyot* 120 (2008), s.p.

⁵⁵ Elena KOL-YA‘AKOV, *Salvage Excavations at Neshor-Ramla Quarry, Vol. 1*, Haifa, Zinman Institute of Archaeology, University of Haifa, 2010, 99–119.

⁵⁶ Moshe FISCHER, *Ḥorvat Meṣad: a Way-Station on the Jaffa-Jerusalem Road* (Sonia and Marco Nadler Institute of Archaeology Monograph Series, 30), Tel Aviv, Emery and Claire Yass Publications in Archaeology, 2012, 56–57, with further references.

⁵⁷ Yusuf RAGIB, “Les premiers monuments funéraires de l’Islam”, *Annales Islamologiques* 9 (1970), 21–36.

⁵⁸ Milka LEVY-RUBIN, “New Evidence Relating to the Process of Islamization in Palestine in the Early Muslim Period – the Case of Samaria”, *JESHO* 43.3 (2000), 268–271.

Despite the negative circumstances in the history of Palestine in the 7th centuries CE described above, including the collapse of some settlements or a reduction in their size, many others continued to exist. What is important is that this is attested to by the results of excavations in both urban and rural areas.⁵⁹ Thus, the settlement factor alone cannot be seen as the sole and decisive reason for the end of the construction and disappearance of the use of communal tombs in the entire region under discussion.

5. Conclusions

Reconstructing the exact time of the collapse of the tradition of using communal tombs in the provinces of *Palaestina Prima* and *Jund Filasṭīn* is no simple task. The main problem is the large number of such graves with inaccurate dating. Nevertheless, on the basis of selected cases of tombs with preserved furnishings in the form of oil lamps, coins, vessels, etc., it is possible to outline the main trends in this area. Based on the examples of 257 tombs, it was possible to show that starting in the 5th century CE in Judea, Samaria and on the Palestinian Coast, an ever-smaller number of tombs were established for family burials. Based on the information available today, it can be concluded that this practice collapsed in the 7th century CE. However, before this occurred in *Palaestina Prima*, in the 5th and 6th centuries CE there is an increase in other types of communal tombs in the form of monastic crypts. These were not used to place the bodies of the dead among those of deceased family members but were the site of group burials of members of monastic communities not bound by blood ties, but only by faith and the way it was practiced.

Despite the collapse of the custom of establishing new family tombs in the 7th century CE, those created in previous centuries were in many cases still used in the 8th century CE. This indicates that the process of disappearance of this burial custom was very slow and extended over time. Nevertheless, at the end of the first millennium family tombs disappeared from the sepulchral landscape of *Jund Filasṭīn*. The abandonment of this tradition concerned Christians, Jews and Samaritans which is evidence of a clear cultural change.

The gradual disappearance of the foundation and subsequent use of family tombs coincides with other significant changes. In the Byzantine period, a larger number of religious foundations appear, indicating a change in investment mentality. In the first half 7th century CE, traces of the negative impact of the Persian conquest were found in several parts of *Palaestina Prima*, and written sources mention the migration of local people at the same time. Despite the dominant trend of continuity of settlement in the early Islamic period, some archaeological sites were abandoned in the 7th and 8th centuries CE, which resulted in simultaneous abandonment of communal tombs in associated cemeteries. The Islamisation of the local population at that time was quite limited and did not play an important role. However, the small Muslim population present in Palestine at that time had different burial traditions. The followers of this religion did not adopt the custom of communal burials, which did not have a positive effect on the continuity of this custom in subsequent centuries. Only monastic communities were the carrier of this tradition. In the case of a few monasteries, the custom of group burials survived on a small scale after the 8th century CE.

The disappearance of the custom of family burials among the wealthier parts of Palestinian society must have resulted in an increase in the number of simpler burials. This is the case with pit- and cist-graves, which are mostly intended for the burial of the body of one deceased individual. However, such a process is difficult to capture in

⁵⁹ G. AVNI, *The Byzantine-Islamic Transition*, 239–257.

archaeological records and has been identified at only few sites.⁶⁰ However, there should be no doubt about the spread of such graves in the early Islamic period, due to the lack of other possibilities. Thus, there was certainly a flattening of social stratification at the level of burial habits at the end of antiquity. The way to this was paved by the abandonment of the foundation of more monumental communal tombs. After 7th–8th century CE, this form of burial ceased to be an element distinguishing different social groups, with the exception of a few monastic communities.

This process was rooted in long-term mentality, settlement, economic and political change. Certainly, these various factors played a changing role over time. The disappearance of family tombs, however, should not be seen as evidence of the disintegration of the most important cell of society. Undoubtedly, family ties invariably constituted one of the most important cultural elements after the 7th–8th century CE, but from the point of view of an archaeologist, they did not leave such a clear mark on the sepulchral sphere as in earlier centuries.

This transition seems to have had a wider reach and did not only involve the region within the boundaries of *Palaestina Prima/Jund Filasṭīn*. Communal tombs or evidence indicating the time of their foundation after the 6th century CE are also unknown in other parts of Syria-Palestine,⁶¹ although settlement continued in these areas as well. Thus, the disappearance of communal tombs would be a supra-regional phenomenon that has not been noticed by researchers dealing with the problem of cultural change during the Byzantine-Islamic transition period.

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Figure caption

Figure 1. Plans for various types of tombs. A. cist- and pit-graves; B. tomb with *loculi*; C. tomb with *arcosolia*; D. hypogeum with troughs; E. the so-called Tomb of the Prophets (Drawing by M. Gwiazda).

Figure 2. Map of *Palaestina Prima/Jund Filasṭīn* indicating communal tombs. Black dots mark the sites included in the statistics. Gray mark sites not included. The numbers on the map refer to the site names in Table 1 (Drawing by M. Gwiazda and J. Chyla).

Figure 3. Number of communal tombs used by century (Drawing by M. Gwiazda).

Figure 4. Number of new communal tombs by century (Drawing by M. Gwiazda).

Figure 5. Number of abandoned communal tombs by century (Drawing by M. Gwiazda).

Figure 6 Maps of the distribution of communal tombs in the 4th, 6th, 8th and 10th centuries CE (Drawing by M. Gwiazda and J. Chyla).

⁶⁰ Jerusalem: G. AVNI, *The Byzantine-Islamic Transition*, 144; Bet Guvrin: G. AVNI, U. DAHARI, A. KLONER, *The Necropolis of Bet Guvrin*, 120.

⁶¹ For a review of archaeological evidence in Transjordan and Syria see: Howard P. KRUG, “Comparative Roman-Byzantine tombs in Transjordan”, in: Samuel D. WATERHOUSE (ed.), *The Necropolis of Hesban. A Typology of Tombs* (Hesban, 10), Berrien Springs, Andrews University Press, 1998, 134–174; A. SARTRE-FAURIAT, *Des tombeaux et des morts*; Marc GRIESHEIMER, “Cimetères et tombeaux des villages de la Syrie du Nord”, *Syria* 74 (1997), 165–211.

Table 1. List of sites with communal tombs included in the statistics.

Site no	Site name	Tombs quant.
1	Ain Yabrud	1
2	Ar'ara	2
3	Ashqelon	4
4	Barqa	1
5	Beit 'Anun (Beth 'Anoth)	3
6	Beit Fajjar	1
7	Beit Guvrin (Eleutheropolis)	8
8	Beit Nattif	1
9	Ben Shemen	1
10	Beth Loya, Khirbet Lehi	1
11	Caesarea Maritima	1
12	Daliya region site 120	1
13	el Jalil	1
14	'En Lavan	1
15	'En Yabrud	1
16	Er Ram	1
17	Et Taiyiba	2
18	Gelilot	1
19	Gezer	30
20	Giv'at Sharet, Bet Shemesh	2
21	Hafez Hayyim	1
22	Horvat Ashdod-Yam	2
23	Horvat Berachot	1
24	Horvat Burgin	1
25	Horvat Ehud	1
26	Horvat Gader	1
27	Horvat Hani / Khirbet el Burj el-Haniya	1
28	Horvat Hanut	3
29	Horvat Horesh	3
30	Horvat Kelah	1
31	Horvat Kishor	1
32	Horvat Midras	1
33	Horvat Thala	2
34	Horvat Zikhrin	1
35	'Ir Gannim	1
36	Itamar	2
37	Jaffa	9
38	Jatt	2
39	Jerusalem	56
40	Kafr Bara	1
41	Kefar 'Ara	1
42	Kefar Shemaryahu (Apollonia/Sozousa)	7
43	Khirbet 'Amurieh	1
44	Khirbet Deir Sallam	1
45	Khirbet el Bira	2
46	Khirbet el Hadra	1
47	Khirbet el Kiliya	1
48	Khirbet el'Aura / Tel Barukh	8
49	Khirbet Jemameh (Ruhama)	1
50	Khirbet Kafr Qari'	1
51	Khirbet Kheibar	1
52	Khirbet Sabiya, Kefar Sava	1
53	Khirbet Umm er Rus (Horvat Beth Bad)	1
54	Khirbet Umm Leisun	3
55	Khirbet Umm Tabun / Or ha-Ner	1
56	Khirbet Umm Zaqum	1
57	Luzit	3
58	Mahatt el Urdi (Kibbutz Bet Guvrin)	1
59	Massu'ot Yizhaq	1
60	Mazor (East), Nahshonim	2
61	Meser	2
62	Mishmar David	2
63	Monastery of Euthymius	2
64	Motza (Colonia, Qalunya)	1
65	Moza 'Illit	1
66	Mughar el Sharaf, Kefar Vitkin	1
67	Nahshon	1
68	Netiv Ha-Lamed He	1
69	Or 'Aqiva	1
70	Qedumim	2
71	Qula	2
72	Rafidiya (Sechem)	1
73	Ramat Razi'el	1
74	Ramla, Nesher	5
75	Rammun	1
76	Ras Abu Dahud	2

77	Regevim	2
78	Salim	1
79	Samaria (Sebaste)	7
80	Shechem (Neapolis)	5
81	Shi'b 'Awad (M)	1
82	Shoham	1
83	Silat el Dahr	1
84	Tel Hayim	1
85	Tel Masos, Khirbet el Msas	1
86	Tel Mevorakh	1
87	Tel Rosh Ha'ayin	1

88	Tell en Nasbeh	5
89	Tell Qasile	2
90	Tell Umm el 'Amr, Gaza region	1
91	Tsur Yitzhak	2
92	Wadi Qelt, Monastery of St. George of Choziba	3
93	Zuqei Hotem	1
94	Zur Natan, Horvat Migdal	1

A**5 m**

Sea of Galilee

N

Dead Sea

map by M. Gwiazda, J.M.Chyla
Service Layer Credits: Sources: Esri, USGS, NOAA

0 25 50 Km

USED TOMBS

NEW TOMBS

ABANDONED TOMBS

4TH C.

map by M. Gwiazda, J.M.Chyla
Service Layer Credits: Sources: Esri, USGS, NOAA

6TH C.

map by M. Gwiazda, J.M.Chyla
Service Layer Credits: Sources: Esri, USGS, NOAA

8TH C.

map by M. Gwiazda, J.M.Chyla
Service Layer Credits: Sources: Esri, USGS, NOAA

10TH C.

map by M. Gwiazda, J.M.Chyla
Service Layer Credits: Sources: Esri, USGS, NOAA